

Assessment of National Board for Arabic and Islamic Studies (NBAIS) Curriculum on Implementation of Qur'anic Memorization in North-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study assessed the relationship between availability of resources and the implementation of Qur'anic memorization curriculum content of NBAIS in North West, Nigeria. The objectives of the study are to: find out the availability of learning resources and the implementation of Qur'anic memorization curriculum content of NBAIS in senior Arabic and Islamic secondary schools; examine the availability of Qur'anic teachers used in the implementation of Qur'anic memorization curriculum content in senior Arabic and Islamic secondary schools. Two research questions and hypotheses in line with the objectives guided the study. The study was survey design. The instruments were validated by the experts. Mann Whitney u test was used to test the hypotheses. The finding revealed that: there was a significant difference between the availability of learning resources in senior Tahfeez and Islamic secondary schools and that of senior Arabic and Islamic secondary schools in the implementation of Qur'anic memorization curriculum content. There was no significant difference between the availability of teachers in senior Tahfeez and Islamic secondary schools and that of Senior Arabic and Islamic secondary schools in the implementation of Qur'anic memorization curriculum content. The study concludes among others that; available Qur'anic memorization teachers must be provided for effective implementation of Qur'anic memorization curriculum content more especially in senior Arabic and Islamic secondary schools. The study recommended among others that; there is need for to providing more human and material resources especially in senior Arabic and Islamic secondary schools, for qualitative Qur'anic memorizers in the schools.

Keywords: Implementation, Qur'anic memorization, curriculum, NBAIS.

Introduction

The research is based on two theories; forgotten or disremembering learning theory and theory of curriculum implementation. But specifically, the research is built upon forgotten or disremembering learning theory. One of the early studies in the mechanism of forgotten or disremembering theory was that of the German Psychologist Hermann Ebbinghaus cited in Memon (2020). Ebbinghaus used himself as the sole subject in the experiment; he memorized lists of three letter syllable words, two consonants and one vowel in the middle. In the experiment, he came up with the fact that learning is always affected by prior knowledge and understanding, he figured out that he would need something that would be memorized easily without prior cognitive associations. Forgotten or disremembering learning theory is the apparent loss or modification of knowledge or any information already encoded and stored in an individual's short or long-term memory. It is a gradual process in which old memories are unable to be recalled from memory storage. Problems with remembering, learning and retaining new information are a few of the most common complaints of older adults. The researches show that retention improves with increased rehearsal. This improvement occurs because the rehearsal helps to transfer information into long-term memory which is the same thing as the issue of Qur'anic memorization, the more someone reads the Qur'anic verses the stronger Qur'anic

Assessment of National Board for Arabic ... (Abdullahi, et al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8381607>

memorization will be. In chapter 87 verse 6 the Almighty God says: “we will make you recite so you shall not forget”. Therefore, Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) himself was commanded to read the Qur’an frequently.

For me, I have been commanded to serve the Lord of this city, Him who has sanctified it and to whom (belong) all things: And I am commanded to be of those who bow in Islam to Allah’s will, And to rehearse the Qur’an: and if any accept guidance, they do it for the good of their own souls, and if any stray, say: I am only a Warner (Qur’an 27: 91-92)

One of the early contributions to the theory of curriculum implementation was that of Schon. Faisal (2014) reported Schon to have said. He based his theory on the observed technological changes which he described as “pervasive”. He thoroughly examined these models of Schon and discovered that his main focus was continuing process of transformation. Schon then mentioned out that institutions called “learning system” should be developed in order to bring about their own continuing transformation. Thus, his centre of focus is system of diffusion. Faisal (2014), identified three evolving models from Schon’s work:

1. Centre Periphery Model (CPM)
2. The Proliferation Centre Model (PCM)
3. Shifting Centre Model (SCM).

This study is hinged to only two models of curriculum implementation which are; Centre Periphery Model and Proliferation Centre Model.

In the Central Periphery Model (CPM), the implementation is centrally controlled either by the government or an agency. The experts that monitor the implementation, the resources required and the training facilities are all centrally controlled by the agency charged with the responsibilities for the implementation spreads or diffuses into the periphery or other parts (Faisal 2014). For the system to work effectively there is a need for adequate communication network, effective supply of materials and a constant monitoring of feedback for the periphery. Thus, in this regard, the National Board for Arabic and Islamic Studies (NBAIS) through Federal ministry of education is responsible for design, curriculum development and issuance of the certificates for senior Tahfeez and Islamic secondary schools; and they are working with states ministries of education in handling the teaching and learning the Qur’anic memorization contents and the Islamic studies curriculum for Senior Arabic and Islamic secondary schools. Curriculum and certificate is provided by NBAIS while teachers and other facilities are provided by the states governments.

The National Board for Arabic and Islamic Studies as National Examination Body which is responsible for curriculum evaluation and issuance the certificate of Senior Arabic and Islamic secondary school Students and also are working with States ministries of education to ensure the successful implementation of Islamic studies in general and Qur’anic memorization contents of NBAIS in particular. This means that the National Board for Arabic and Islamic Studies (NBAIS) serves as Centres while States ministries of education serves as peripheries.

The Proliferation Centre Model (PCM) maintains that for the implementation to be successful there must be two centres namely primary and secondary centres. According to Ahmed (2016), the proliferation of centre model maintains that in implementation there should be both primary and secondary implementation centres. The primary centres are responsible for managing the secondary centres. They provide them with training materials and the resources model. The secondary centres engaged in diffusing or spreading the change in their individual area of control. This resembles what we have in the National Primary Education Commission (now UBEC). The commission means the primary school Board at National level, while the State Boards coordinate the affairs in the various local governments and feedback to the commission. For this to succeed there should be sufficient materials and training facilities at the centres. There should also be an effective communication network, adequate finance and effective supervision. Therefore, this model is relevant to the study in the sense that, the National Board for Arabic and Islamic Studies (NBAIS) serves as primary centres which are responsible in providing the Qur’anic memorization contents of NBAIS to be taught through secondary centres in the three (3) states of North-west, Nigeria.

Memorizing the Qur’an is a commitment that expresses one’s effort to please Allah by committing His words into memory. The Muslims faithful believe that the Qur’an is the speech and commandments of Allah. In this, precision and accuracy in the articulation of the Qur’anic verses is compulsory. The word Qur’an derived from the Arabic language and from the root “qara’a” which means to read or to recite. Al-Qur’an as a noun therefore means the reading or the recitation. Technically, refers to the book revealed to the messenger of Allah, Muhammad (PBUH) in Arabic and transmitted to us from Him through an authentic continuous revelation. The encounter of Prophet Muhammad, peace be upon him (PBUH) with angel Gabriel in His retreat cave of Hira on 21st Ramadhan (613CE) at the age of 40 was a momentous event, (Ramdane & Souad 2017). The simple five verses revealed upon Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) which started with the single word of command *iqra*

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(read) signified the beginning of the revelation which lasted for twenty-three years (23yrs). The Qur'an is unique to be preserved in memory, the *hifz* (memorization). The word *hifz* (memorization) itself, though now it's used in the limited sense of memorization which includes both understanding and practice. According to Murad (2013), *hifz* (memorization) is an essential means to make the Qur'an penetrate one's heart. It is not a mechanical, ritual act; it is an act of high spiritual and devotional importance. Only through *hifz* (memorization) one can read the Qur'an in prayers and ponder over its meaning while he is standing in the presence of God. Apart from that it makes the Qur'an flow on tongues, resides in minds, dwell in hearts and becomes a constant companion. That is one of the reasons the Prophet peace be upon him at his own house the main priority then was to teaching His companions the tenets of the religion, reciting, memorizing the Qur'anic passages and interpreting its meanings. The National Board for Arabic and Islamic Studies (NBAIS) according to Lawal (2014), is one and only National Body which has the curriculum of full Qur'anic memorization for senior Arabic and Islamic secondary schools. The main objective of NBAIS is to promote and inculcate;

1. the good Qur'anic recitation among the Nigerians' students at senior Tahfeez/Arabic and Islamic secondary schools' level;
2. and understanding the meanings of the Qur'anic content among Muslims' students in senior Arabic and Islamic Secondary Schools across the country;
3. Memorization of the whole Qur'an by Senior Tahfeez (Qur'anic memorization) and Islamic Secondary Schools across the Country.

Teachers are considered as the most important persons in the teaching and learning process why because, without their knowledge, experience and competency, good instructional process, the achievement will not be realistic. This means that the teachers need to be trained on philosophy of the programme, content of the curriculum as well as pedagogical approach Garba, (1996) in Jikas (2015). From the aforementioned, it can be simply understand that adequate and competent teachers, relevant learning resources, relevant curriculum Qur'anic memorization content must to be provided in order to produce qualitative reciters and memorizers of the Qur'an at different levels in senior Tahfeez and Islamic secondary schools; as such, the researchers aim at assessing the National Board for Arabic and Islamic Studies (NBAIS) Curriculum on implementation of Qur'anic memorization in North-West, Nigeria

For the successful teaching and learning Qur'anic memorization curriculum content of NBAIS, adequate number of human and material resources must be provided. Islam always put emphasis on the importance of teaching and learning the Qur'an. However, there are still many students who are left behind in terms of their Qur'anic reading, memorization and understanding due to so many reasons. The programme of Qur'anic memorization is design to produce Qur'anic memorizers, but some students are being able to complete their memorization. A teacher who can recite the Qur'an with fluency and smoothly as well as articulating every letter from its articulation point and giving the letter its right and dues of characteristics will be considered as model teacher who expertise in Qur'anic recitation. Therefore, the programme is designed for Qur'anic memorization but many students are not being able to complete their memorization.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study are to:

1. Examine Tahfiz and Arabic senior secondary schools' availability of instructional materials and implementation of Qur'anic memorization curriculum content knowledge in North-West, Nigeria.
2. Assess Tahfiz and Arabic senior secondary schools' availability of teachers and implementation of Qur'anic memorization curriculum content knowledge in North-West, Nigeria.

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between Tahfiz and Arabic senior secondary schools regarding availability of instructional materials and implementation of Qur'anic memorization curriculum content in North-West, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant difference between Tahfiz and Arabic senior secondary schools regarding availability of teachers and implementation of Qur'anic memorization curriculum content in North-West, Nigeria.

Methodology

The study adopted the descriptive survey design. The study targeted all principals in Senior Tahfeez and Islamic Public Secondary Schools in the North-West, Nigeria principals were selected to give the information on the availability of teachers. There are total number of three hundred and twenty-eight (328) schools which is the same total number of principals in public Senior Tahfeez and Islamic secondary schools in the North-West, Nigeria (Kano Kaduna & Katsina), The research advisor (2006) (in Haruna, 2010) was used for determining sample size. Therefore, one hundred and ninety-six (196) considered

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for this study as the sample size. Therefore, in this study, random sampling technique, purposive sampling technique and proportionate sampling techniques were used for this research. The researcher used simple random sampling technique to choose three (3) states from the seven (7) in North-western, states. The hypotheses tested using Mann Whitney U-test at 0.05 significant level.

Results

Hypothesis 1

there is significant difference between Tahfiz and Arabic senior secondary schools' availability of instructional materials and implementation of Qur'anic memorization curriculum content knowledge in North-West, Nigeria.

Table 1: Mann-Whitney U Test Analysis of Difference in the Mean Ranks Scores on the Availability of Learning Resources in the Implementation of Qur'anic Memorization Curriculum Content of NBAIS in Senior Tahfeez and Islamic Secondary Schools in the North-West, Nigeria

Groups	N	MR	SR	U	Z	p-value	Decision
STIS	126	163.13	27568.50	11176.300	-0.586	0.603	Rejected
SIS	71	161.82	25081.50				

* *Significant at P > 0.05*

The table 1 above presents the result of the Mann-Whitney U test conducted to compare the mean ranks scores on the availability of learning resources in the implementation of Qur'anic memorization curriculum content in Senior Tahfeez and Islamic Secondary Schools in North-west, Nigeria. The result of the analysis indicated that there was significant difference in the mean ranks scores between Senior Tahfeez and Islamic Secondary Schools (STIS) (163.13) and that of Senior Arabic and Islamic Secondary Schools (SIS) (161.82), with (U=11176.300; Z= -0.586, p =0.603>0.05). Therefore, based on the result obtained from the data, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between Tahfiz and Arabic senior secondary schools' availability of teachers and implementation of Qur'anic memorization curriculum content in North-West, Nigeria.

Table 2: Mann-Whitney U Test Analysis of Difference in the Mean Ranks Scores on the Availability of Teachers in the Implementation of Qur'anic Memorization Curriculum Content of NBAIS in Senior Tahfeez and Islamic Secondary Schools in the North-West, Nigeria.

Groups	N	MR	SR	U	Z	p-value	Decision
STIS	126	104.27	6272.50	3716.500	-1.921	0.054	Accepted
SIS	71	88.35	13033.50				

Not Significant at P > 0.05

The table 2 above presents the result of the Mann-Whitney U test conducted to compare the mean ranks scores on the availability of teachers and the implementation of Qur'anic memorization curriculum content in Senior Tahfeez and Islamic Secondary Schools in North-west, Nigeria. The result of the analysis indicated that there is no significant difference in the mean ranks scores between Senior Tahfeez and Islamic Secondary Schools (STIS) (104.27) and that of Senior Arabic and Islamic Secondary Schools (SIS)(88.35), with (U=3716.500; Z= -1.921, p =0.054≤0.05). Therefore, since the p value is less than equal to the alpha value (0.05) the null hypothesis was accepted.

Discussion of Findings

The finding on the assessment of National Board for Arabic and Islamic Studies (NBAIS) Curriculum on implementation of Qur'anic memorization in North-West, Nigeria is as follows; the result of the analysis indicated that there was significant difference in the mean ranks scores between Senior Tahfeez and Islamic Secondary Schools (STIS) (163.13)

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and that of Senior Arabic and Islamic Secondary Schools (SIS)(161.82), with ($U=11176.300$; $Z= -0.586$, $p =0.603>0.05$). Therefore, based on the result obtained from the data, the hypothesis is hereby rejected. The finding of this study is agree with the finding of Abdullahi and Ahmed (2021), on the assessment of the implementation of National Board for Arabic and Islamic studies' (NBAIS) in Kano state metropolis. The finding revealed that there were inadequate learning resources for the successful implementation of Islamic studies NBAIS curriculum in Kano metropolis. The finding also is in accordance with the finding of Muhammed (2017), on assessment of the availability and utilization of instructional materials for teaching and learning of Islamic studies in junior secondary schools in Kaduna state, Nigeria. The finding revealed that there were inadequate learning materials in the schools. The finding of this study also confirmed the finding of Habib (2014), on assessment of Islamic studies curriculum in junior secondary schools in Zamfara state. The finding revealed that there were inadequate learning resources for teaching Islamic studies curriculum at junior secondary schools in Zamfara, State.

The finding on the assessment of National Board for Arabic and Islamic Studies (NBAIS) Curriculum on implementation of Qur'anic memorization in North-West, Nigeria are as follows: the finding of the analysis indicated that there is no significant difference in the mean ranks scores between Senior Tahfeez and Islamic Secondary Schools (STIS)(104.27) and that of Senior Arabic and Islamic Secondary Schools (SIS)(88.35), with ($U=3716.500$; $Z= -1.921$, $p =0.054\leq 0.05$). Therefore, since the p value is less than equal to the alpha value (0.05) the hypothesis which states that there is no significance difference between the assessment of National Board for Arabic and Islamic Studies (NBAIS) Curriculum on implementation of Qur'anic memorization in North-West, Nigeria. is hereby accepted. The finding of the study confirmed the finding of Sha'aban (2015), on the challenges of teaching Islamic religious education on spiritual and academic performance of secondary schools' students in Nairobi Kenya. The finding revealed that there was shortage of Islamic religious education in Kenya. The finding is not similar to the finding of Jikas (2015), on the assessment of the implementation of Islamic curriculum in senior secondary schools in Jigawa State.

Conclusion

Teaching and learning Qur'anic memorization needs availability of learning resources, the study discovered there were inadequate learning resources in the schools more especially in senior Arabic and Islamic secondary schools. This was identified as very significant factor which negatively affected the Qur'anic memorization in Senior Tahfeez and Islamic Secondary Schools in North-west, Nigeria. Finally, Qur'anic teachers were not enough in the schools. Teachers were identified as backbone of any curriculum implementation without adequate and competent Qur'anic teachers; effective teaching and learning Qur'anic memorization will jeopardize.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Relevant and necessary learning resources should adequately be provided to enhance the implementation of teaching and learning Qur'anic memorization curriculum content in senior Tahfeez and Islamic secondary schools in North-west, Nigeria.
2. Government should collaborate with Parent-Teachers' Association, Qur'anic reciters' Association of Nigeria to provide professionals and adequate number of Qur'anic teachers so as to achieve the general aim of Tahfeez programme which is in reality means the full and complete Qur'anic memorization in the school

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